

Cache-enabled Millimeter Wave Cellular Networks with Clusters

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Abstract—Wireless content caching in cellular networks is an efficient way to reduce the service delay and alleviate backhaul pressure. For the benefits of sharing spectral and storage resources, clustering in cached networks has recently attracted significant research interests. Meanwhile, since the multimedia content (e. g., video) of caching networks may require a huge transmission rates, millimeter wave (mmWave) communication is considered to be an efficient transmission scheme for cache-enabled networks. We investigate the ergodic rate and average service delay for typical user terminal (UT) in the clustered cache-enabled small cell networks (SCN) and ultra dense networks (UDN) with mmWave channels. In SCN, each cluster consists of cache-enabled UTs, and in the UDN a cluster is formed by cache-enabled UTs and small base stations (SBSs) with non-uniform caching capacity. The clusters are assumed to be discs and content sharing is only possible within clusters through mmWave device-to-device (D2D) tier and SBS tier communications. With stochastic geometry methods, the distributions of content sharing distance and signal-to-interference-noise-ratio (SINR) of typical UT in a cluster are derived for both SCN and UDN scenarios. To minimize the average service delay in high SINR region, we provide an algorithm to jointly optimize caching scheme for SBSs and UTs. By simulations, we validate our theoretical analysis and the performance of proposed caching scheme. The numerical results also show that there exists best radius in the design of cluster for UDNs.

Index Terms—Caching, D2D communication, heterogeneous networks, ultra dense networks, mmWave, clustering.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless data traffic has experienced tremendous growth in recent years. According to [1], [2], the data traffic is increasingly concentrated to hotspots and is expected to increase almost tenfold by 2020 compared with 2016. The heavy traffic is normally connected to the core network (CN) through backhauling, which may have limited capacity. This makes the backhaul a bottleneck of wireless networks. One promising technology to reduce the expensive usage of the backhaul and to shorten service delay is wireless caching [3]–[11]. In a cache-enabled system, storage memory is utilized to prefetch popular contents in small cells during off-peak hours before being requested by user terminals (UTs). The requests can be served directly through wireless links if the requested contents are already stored in the local small base stations (SBSs) instead of fetching from the remote CN. Thus the service delay can be largely reduced. Since the UTs, e. g.,

smart phones and laptops, are normally equipped with storage units, popular contents can also be stored at the local cache of UTs. Then the requests can be served locally if the requested contents are already available at local storage. Moreover, the saved contents can also be shared via device-to-device (D2D) communication among neighboring UTs [12]–[18], through which the backhaul bandwidth and service delay can be further reduced. However, due to the co-channel interference caused by D2D communications, and the limited energy resources for UTs, the resource management for D2D communications should be well designed. In [15], a joint D2D link scheduling and power allocation problem is formulated in order to maximize the system throughput. The trade-off between the energy efficiency (EE) and spectral efficiency (SE) is investigated in [19]. The cluster-based D2D communication is studied in [20]–[24]. Reference [20] presents a system model where the cell is divided into clusters. Each cluster is formed by UTs with caching, and the UTs in a same cluster can share stored contents via D2D communication. With clustering, the same time-frequency resource can be reused in each cluster, through which the intra-cluster interference can be avoided. A cluster-based multicast transmission method for D2D communication with the objective of decreasing the data distribution time is proposed in [21]. In [22], a probabilistic caching scheme is designed to minimize the energy consumption of a clustered cache-enabled D2D network. Reference [23] investigates and maximizes the cache offloading gain and rate coverage probability for a clustered D2D caching network, where a sub-optimal caching solution is obtained. Besides, a joint caching and spectrum partitioning scheme is proposed to reduce the average service delay for clustered D2D networks in [24].

Meanwhile, as one promising technology for the fifth generation (5G) and beyond mobile networks, millimeter wave (mmWave) communication can support higher data rate than microwave communications [25]–[27]. According to references [28]–[30], mmWave communications can facilitate popular content exchange in cache-enabled small cell networks (SCNs), especially for video streaming, which may require very high transmission rates [31]. The offloading gain of D2D-aware device caching with mmWave D2D communication is revealed in [28]. While the successful content delivery probability is studied in [29]. In [30], the success probabilities and area spectral efficiencies are analyzed in a novel cache-enabled heterogeneous networks (HetNets), where macro base stations (BSs) with traditional sub-6 GHz are overlaid by dense mmWave pico BSs. Besides, it is shown that combining caching and mmWave at SBSs can significantly reduce the

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connection and retrieval delays [31]. Thus, it is expected that mmWave will be widely used in mobile networks and it is valuable to investigate wireless caching networks with mmWave communications, which is significantly different from traditional microwave communications in terms of channel models, performance and design principles etc. In the above-mentioned works, none of them investigates the clustering scheme for cache-enabled mmWave cellular networks.

Another capacity-increasing approach in 5G systems is deploying ultra dense networks (UDN), where the network is closer to UTs than traditional SCNs. Different from SCN, the density of access points (APs), including macro BSs, micro BSs (pico BSs and femto BSs), and relays, are much higher than that in SCN. The distance between the APs and UTs is further decreased. Thus, the network capacity is increased with UDN [32]. The cache-enabled SCN is investigated in [33]–[37], while the cache-enabled UDN is investigated in [38]–[43]. Reference [35] considers a cluster-centric SCN with the combined design of cooperative caching and transmission policy. In [36], UTs with similar content popularity are grouped into a cluster, and served by a same SBS. As for UDN, a clustering approach is considered as a promising way to simplify the topology structures of UDN and to reduce complexity [38]. In [39], the user-centric cooperative interference mitigation strategy is proposed, where dense SBSs are able to store contents. In [42], the small cells are grouped into disjoint clusters. However, there are no results investigating the clustering scheme for the cache-enabled mmWave SCN and UDN, to our knowledge.

We focus on studying the effect of cluster size, caching policies and capacity of UTs and SBSs by characterizing the ergodic rate and average service delay for typical UT in clustered cache-enabled SCN and UDN. The main contributions of this paper are listed as follows.

- We investigate the service delay for typical UT located at the center of a cluster in cache-enabled SCN and UDN, where both mmWave D2D and SBS tiers are involved.
- We derive the exact distribution of serving distance for typical UT in cache-enabled SCN and UDN with clusters, based on which the closed-form expression of SINRs with mmWave communications are calculated through *Gaussian-Chebyshev quadrature* approximation.
- We derive the exact ergodic rate and average service delay for the typical UT in SCN and UDN scenarios. To gain further insights, we assume having a high SINR and the closed-form approximation for ergodic rates is derived.
- To minimize the average service delay of typical UT, we propose an *Alternate Optimization* based algorithm to jointly optimize the caching policy for SBSs and UTs in both SCN and UDN scenarios.
- Numerical results show that: 1) in mmWave SCN and UDN, the approximations of SINRs and ergodic rates in high SINR region coincide with theoretical results; 2) the proposed caching scheme can achieve smaller service delay compared with other policies; 3) there exists a best size of clusters in cache-enabled SCN upon the service delay of typical UT.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. We present the model of clustered cache-enabled SCN and UDN with mmWave communication in Section II. Then for both scenarios, the distributions of content transmission and SINR for typical UT are provided in Section III. Furthermore, in Section IV, ergodic rate and average service delay for typical UT are derived. Numerical experiments are presented to evaluate the performance of the clustering scheme in Section V. Finally we make conclusions in Section VI.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

The system model of clustered cache-enabled networks with mmWave channel is illustrated in Fig. 1. We assume that the locations of UTs follow a two-dimensional homogeneous Poisson Point Process (PPP) Φ_1 with density λ_1 . The locations of SBSs are spatially distributed following a two-dimensional homogeneous PPP Φ_2 (Φ'_2) with density λ_2 (λ'_2) in SCN(UDN) [44]. The popular contents are denoted by $\mathcal{F} = \{1, \dots, F\}$ ($F \in \mathbb{N}$). Without loss of generality, we assume that each content has the same length l , and they are stored as a whole at each UT and SBS. The storage capacity for UT and SBS is Θ_1 and Θ_2 respectively. Notation is summarized in Table I.

Fig. 1: (a) Cache-enabled mmWave SCN with clusters where $\lambda_1 \gg \lambda_2$; (b) Cache-enabled mmWave UDN with clusters with comparable λ_1 and λ_2 .

A. Network Architecture

We consider clustering schemes for two scenarios, where clusters are disjoint discs with common radius d . Fig. 1 (a) shows the clustered cache-enabled SCN, where the density of SBSs is much lower than that of UTs, i. e. $\lambda_1 \gg \lambda_2$. For this scenario, cells are divided into virtual clusters as demonstrated in [20]. Within each cluster, UTs can share stored contents with each other through D2D links, where the content sharing is completed in one hop to reduce the delay and complex

TABLE I: Notation and simulation parameters

Param.	Meaning	Value
d	Radius of clusters	
N_d	Number of D2D links in each cluster	
Π_1, Π_2	Caching policies of UTs and SBSs	
Θ_1, Θ_2	Caching capacities of UTs and SBSs	
P_1, P_2	Transmission power of D2D and SBS tier communication	
M	Nagami- M	3
r_d	D2D collaboration distance	15 m
F	Number of popular content	100
l	File length	0.1 Gb
η	Zipf shape parameter	{0.9, 1.2}
Θ_1	Cache capacity of UTs	{0.5, 0.8} Gb
Φ_1, λ_1	UT PPP and density	$\lambda_1 = 10^{-2} / \text{m}^2$
Φ_2, λ_2	SBS PPP and density in SCN	$\lambda_2 = 5 \times 10^{-5} / \text{m}^2$
Φ'_2, λ'_2	SBS PPP and density in UDN	$\lambda'_2 = 5 \times 10^{-3} / \text{m}^2$
W	Bandwidth	1 GHz
σ^2	Thermal noise	$-174 + 10 \log_{10} W$ +10 dB
α_L	Pathloss exponent of LOS	{2.5, 3}
α_N	Pathloss exponent of NLOS	3.5
g_M	Main-lobe gain	$10^{1.8}$ dB
g_m	Side-lobe gain	10^{-2} dB
φ_m	Main-lobe beamwidth	$\pi/18$
R_{\max}	Maximum achievable rate	2 Gbps
P_0	Interfering SBS power	30 dBm
T_0	Backhaul delay	0.1 s
t	Controlling parameter	30

communication protocols for multi-hop transmission. When a content is requested by a UT, the request will be served immediately if the content is stored at the cache. Otherwise, the desired content can be obtained from the nearest UT where it is available. When the requested content is not available in the cluster, it needs to be retrieved from the cache of the nearest SBS or the CN.

While for the cache-enabled UDN shown in Fig. 1 (b), the considered area is divided into virtual clusters that consist of SBSs and UTs. In UDN, the density of the SBS is comparable with that of UT. Hence in the design of the clustering scheme, we need to take both SBSs and UTs into account.

According to resource sharing schemes in [45]–[48], we assume that in each cluster, local D2D links and D2B/B2B links reuse the same radio resource. That is, concurrent transmissions of D2D and D2B/B2B links are available. References [45], [46] have shown that the use of directional antenna and high propagation loss in mmWave bands can result in relatively lower mutual interference or even no interference by properly selecting the concurrent links formed by geographically distributed wireless devices. Thus, we ignore the interference for concurrent transmissions in each cluster, which may provide an upper bound of system performance. To make the interference of D2D links between clusters negligible, according to [20], we allow the maximum number of D2D links in a disc of radius d as $N_d = \lceil d/r_d \rceil$, where r_d is D2D collaboration distance [20]. With multiple D2D links in a cluster, we use

orthogonal radio resource (frequency or time) to avoid mutual intra-cluster interference among D2D links [47]–[50]. For simplicity, we consider equal bandwidth partition among D2D links in each cluster. Our models (SCN and UDN), however, are applicable to any radio allocation schemes and non-orthogonal resource allocation schemes (e.g., non-orthogonal multiplexing access [51]).

B. Transmission Model with mmWave Channel

We assume the connections between SBS and UT, UT and UT are modeled as mmWave channels, where the D2D tier and SBS tier share the same frequency resource. Then we consider directional beamforming and use a sector model to analyze effective beam pattern [52], [53]. Let $G_{g_M, g_m, \varphi_m}(\varphi)$ denote the sectored antenna pattern, where φ is the angle off the boresight direction, $\varphi_m \in [0, 2\pi]$ is main-lobe beamwidth, g_M (dB) is main-lobe gain, and g_m (dB) is side-lobe gain. Then the antenna gain between a transmitter and a receiver is a discrete random variable, which is described by

$$G = \begin{cases} g_M^2, & \Pr_{\text{MM}} = \frac{\varphi_m^2}{4\pi^2}; \\ g_M g_m, & \Pr_{\text{Mm}} = \frac{(2\pi - \varphi_m)\varphi_m}{4\pi^2}; \\ g_m g_M, & \Pr_{\text{mM}} = \frac{(2\pi - \varphi_m)\varphi_m}{4\pi^2}; \\ g_m^2, & \Pr_{\text{mm}} = \frac{(2\pi - \varphi_m)^2}{4\pi^2}, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where \Pr_{lk} ($l, k \in \mathcal{M} = \{m, M\}$) is the probability for antenna gain $g_l g_k$. We further assume that perfect beam alignment can be achieved at the desired link with perfect CSI. Thus, the directivity gain for the desired signal link is $G_0 = g_M^2$.

In both SCN and UDN scenarios, we assume that the bandwidth for each transmission is W . Without loss of generality, we suppose that each user connects only one UT(SBS) when it is served. In addition we consider both path loss and small-scale fading. For small-scale fading of each link, the Nakagami- M fading channel is considered as in [54], [55]. Besides, in SCN and UDN, we consider line-of-sight (LOS) for links within the cluster and non-line-of-sight (NLOS) for links outside the cluster according to [25]. The path loss exponents for the LOS and NLOS links are denoted as α_L and α_N , respectively [27].

C. Caching Model

Similar to [16], we consider homogeneous content preference in SCN and UDN scenarios, where all UTs have the same content preference distribution. In other words, each UT independently and randomly requests contents according to the same popularity distribution $\mathbf{p} \in (0, 1)^{1 \times F}$. According to results in [56], \mathbf{p} follows a Zipf-like distribution, while the element p_f represents the probability of UT requesting content f . Defining the content popularity index as vector $\boldsymbol{\omega} = \{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_F\}$, the request probability of the i -th most popular content ω_i can be calculated as

$$p_{\omega_i} = \frac{i^{-\eta}}{\sum_{j=1}^F j^{-\eta}}, \quad i \in \mathcal{F}, \quad (2)$$

where η is the shape parameter. The vector ω is permutation of \mathcal{F} . All UTs(SBSs) follow the same policy $\Pi_1(\Pi_2)$ (e. g., random caching (RC)) to store contents. Denote the index of cached contents for UT as $\bar{\omega}_{\Pi_1} \subset \omega$ with length Θ_1 , while the index of cached contents for SBS as $\bar{\omega}_{\Pi_2} \subset \omega$ with length Θ_2 . The caching capacity of SBSs and UTs is non-uniform, i. e., $\Theta_2 > \Theta_1$. We define $\text{Pr}_{1,f} \triangleq \Pr\{f \in \bar{\omega}_{\Pi_1}\}$ and $\text{Pr}_{2,f} \triangleq \Pr\{f \in \bar{\omega}_{\Pi_2}\}$. When $\Pi_1(\Pi_2)$ is fixed, the probability $\text{Pr}_{1,f}(\text{Pr}_{2,f})$ is identical among UTs(SBSs).

III. SINR ANALYSIS IN CLUSTERED CACHE-ENABLED NETWORKS

We first present the distribution of transmission distance for a typical UT in clustered SCN and UDN. Then considering mmWave channel in D2D and SBS tiers, the SINR distribution is derived for both scenarios.

A. Distance Distribution in Clustered SCN

Since the density of SBS is much smaller than that of UT, i. e. $\lambda_1 \gg \lambda_2$, SBSs in Φ_2 are located only in a few clusters. Hence we consider a cluster \mathcal{A} with radius d , which does not include a SBS. Moreover, to simplify the analysis, we focus on the typical UT o , which is inserted at the center of \mathcal{A} . As illustrated in Section II, the typical UT can retrieve desired content from neighboring UTs within \mathcal{A} with distance X_1 , or from the nearest SBS with $X_2 (> d)$. The probability density functions (PDFs) of X_1 and X_2 are given in Lemma 1.

Fig. 2: Content sharing within a cluster in cache-enabled mmWave SCN.

Lemma 1. In clustered cache-enabled SCN, for the typical UT o requesting content f , which is located at the center of \mathcal{A} with radius d , the PDF of X_1 is

$$f_{X_1}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{2\bar{\lambda}_{1,f} \pi x e^{-\bar{\lambda}_{1,f} \pi x^2}}{1 - e^{-\bar{\lambda}_{1,f} \pi d^2}}, & 0 \leq x \leq d; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $\bar{\lambda}_{1,f} = \text{Pr}_{1,f} \lambda_1$. The PDF of SBS tier distance X_2 is

$$f_{X_2}(x) = \begin{cases} 2\lambda_2 \pi x e^{-\lambda_2 \pi (x^2 - d^2)}, & d \leq x; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Proof. See Appendix A the Proof of Lemma 1. \square

For the derivation of $f_{X_1}(x)$, we thin the PPP Φ_1 to $\bar{\Phi}_{1,f}$ by only considering the UTs which have desired content f . The derivation of $f_{X_2}(x)$ is based on the condition that content f is not available within \mathcal{A} .

B. SINR Distribution in mmWave SCN

Based on the distance distribution of content sharing in Lemma 1, we then investigate the SINR distribution for the typical UT when mmWave channel is applied. At first the SINR distribution for UT o is derived with mmWave D2D transmission. Let $\mathcal{D}_1 \triangleq \Phi_2 \setminus \mathcal{A}$ and denote $s \in \mathcal{D}_1$ the interference SBS outside of cluster \mathcal{A} . Thus according to [53], the SINR between the typical UT and the serving UT can be expressed as

$$\Gamma_1 = \frac{P_1 G_0 x^{-\alpha_L} |h_0|^2}{I_1 + \sigma^2}, \quad (5)$$

where $I_1 = \sum_{s \in \mathcal{D}_1} P_0 G r_s^{-\alpha_N} |h_u|^2$ is the inter-cluster interference with mmWave channel and r_s is the distance between the interference SBS and typical UT. P_1 is the transmission power of D2D tier, while P_0 is the average transmission power for SBSs within D_1 . Then we derive the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of Γ_1 in the following lemma.

Lemma 2. In cache-enabled mmWave SCN, the CDF of Γ_1 for typical UT requesting f at cluster \mathcal{A} can be approximated as

$$F_{\Gamma_1}(\gamma) \approx \sum_{m=0}^M \binom{M}{m} (-1)^m \sum_{i=1}^t w_i \Psi_{\bar{\lambda}_{1,f}, \lambda_2, \psi_{1,1k}}(u_i), \quad (6)$$

where t is a predefined integer and

$$w_i = \frac{\pi}{t+1} \sin^2\left(\frac{i}{t+1}\pi\right), \quad u_i = \cos\left(\frac{i}{t+1}\pi\right), \quad (7)$$

where $\Psi_{\bar{\lambda}_{1,f}, \lambda_2, \psi_{1,1k}}(u_i)$ is given in (8), $\psi_{1,1k} = \frac{\kappa P_0 G_1 G_k}{M P_1 G_0}$, $\kappa = M(M!)^{-\frac{1}{M}}$, and ${}_2F_1(\cdot, \cdot; \cdot; \cdot)$ is the Gaussian Hypergeometric function.

Proof. See Appendix B the Proof of Lemma 2. \square

To obtain the closed-form expression for $F_{\Gamma_1}(\gamma)$, we adopt Gaussian-Chebyshev quadrature in the derivation, which approximates the definite integral of a function by weighted sum of function values at specified points within the domain of integration. t balances the trade-off between the complexity

$$\Psi_{\bar{\lambda}_{1,f}, \lambda_2, \psi_{1,1k}}(u_i) = \frac{\bar{\lambda}_{1,f} \pi d^2 (u_i + 1)}{2(1 - e^{-\bar{\lambda}_{1,f} \pi d^2}) \sqrt{1 - u_i^2}} e^{-\frac{d^2}{4} \bar{\lambda}_{1,f} \pi (u_i + 1)^2} \times e^{-\frac{m \kappa \gamma \sigma^2 d^{\alpha_L} (u_i + 1)^{\alpha_L}}{2^{\alpha_L} P_1 G_0} - \pi \lambda_2 \sum_{l,k \in M} \text{Pr}_{lk} d^2 ({}_2F_1(M, -\frac{2}{\alpha_N}; 1 - \frac{2}{\alpha_N}; -\gamma m \psi_{1,1k} (u_i + 1)^{\alpha_L} 2^{-\alpha_L} d^{\alpha_L - \alpha_N}) - 1)}. \quad (8)$$

and accuracy of *Gaussian-Chebyshev quadrature* approximation. The detailed derivation of $\Psi_{\bar{\lambda}_{1,f}, \lambda_2, \psi_{1,ik}}(\cdot)$ can be found in Appendix B.

When f is not available for the typical UT in \mathcal{A} , the content will be retrieved from the nearest SBS. Let X_2 denote the distance between the typical UT and the nearest SBS, and \mathcal{A}_2 denote the disc with radius X_2 . Thus, when the nearest SBS provides service, we obtain the SINR for the UT o as

$$I_2 = \frac{P_2 G_0 x^{-\alpha_N} |h_0|^2}{I_2 + \sigma^2}, \quad (9)$$

where $I_2 = \sum_{s \in \mathcal{D}_2} P_0 G r_s^{-\alpha_N} |h_{us}|^2$ is the inter-cluster interference, and r_s is the distance between the interference SBS in $\mathcal{D}_2 \triangleq \Phi_2 \setminus b(o, X_2)$ and UT o , where $b(o, X_2)$ is the disc of radius X_2 centered at o . P_2 is the transmission power of mmWave SBS tier. Following similar approaches in Lemma 2, we can obtain the CDF of I_2 .

Lemma 3. *In cache-enabled mmWave SCN, the CDF of I_2 for typical UT at cluster \mathcal{A} can be approximated as*

$$F_{I_2}(\gamma) \approx \sum_{m=0}^M \binom{M}{m} (-1)^m \sum_{i=1}^t w_i \Lambda_{\lambda_2, \psi_{2,ik}}(u_i), \quad (10)$$

where w_i and u_i are given in (7), and

$$\Lambda_{\lambda_2, \psi_{2,ik}}(u_i) = \frac{8\lambda_2 \pi d^3 e^{\lambda_2 \pi d^2}}{(u_i + 1)^2 \sqrt{1 - u_i^2}} e^{-\frac{4\lambda_2 \pi d^2}{(u_i + 1)^2} - \frac{m\kappa \sigma^2 (2d)^{\alpha_N} \gamma}{P_2 G_0 (u_i + 1)^{\alpha_N}}} \times e^{-\pi \lambda_2 \sum_{l,k \in M} \text{Pr}_{lk} \frac{4d^2}{(u_i + 1)^2} \left(2F_1\left(M, -\frac{2}{\alpha_N}; 1 - \frac{2}{\alpha_N}; -\gamma m \psi_{2,ik}\right) - 1 \right)}, \quad (11)$$

where $\psi_{2,ik} = \frac{\kappa P_0 g_l g_k}{M P_2 G_0}$.

Proof. From the proof of Lemma 2, the CDF of I_2 can be obtained as

$$F_{I_2}(\gamma) \approx \sum_{m=0}^M \binom{M}{m} (-1)^m \mathbb{E}_{X_2} \left[\mathbb{E}_{I_2} \left[e^{-\frac{m\kappa \gamma I_2}{P_2 G_0 x^{-\alpha_N}}} \right] e^{-\frac{m\kappa \gamma \sigma^2}{P_2 G_0 x^{-\alpha_N}}} \right], \quad (12)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}_{I_2} \left[e^{-\frac{m\kappa \gamma I_2}{P_2 G_0 x^{-\alpha_N}}} \right] &= \mathbb{E}_{s \in \mathcal{D}_2} \left[\prod_{s \in \mathcal{D}_2} \mathbb{E}_{G, h_u} \left[e^{-\frac{m\kappa \gamma P_0 G r_s^{-\alpha_N} |h_{us}|^2}{P_2 G_0 x^{-\alpha_N}}} \right] \right] \\ &= e^{-\lambda_2 \sum_{l,k \in M} \text{Pr}_{lk} \int_x^\infty \int_0^{2\pi} \left(1 - (1 + \gamma m \psi_{2,ik} x^{\alpha_N} r_s^{-\alpha_N})^{-M} \right) r_s dr_s d\theta} \\ &= e^{-\pi \lambda_2 \sum_{l,k \in M} \text{Pr}_{lk} x^2 \left(2F_1\left(M, -\frac{2}{\alpha_N}; 1 - \frac{2}{\alpha_N}; -\gamma m \psi_{2,ik}\right) - 1 \right)}. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Then substituting (13) into (12) and calculating the expectation over X_2 , the final result (10) is derived. \square

Similar to $\Psi_{\bar{\lambda}_{1,f}, \lambda_2, \psi_{1,ik}}(\cdot)$, the derivation of $\Lambda_{\lambda_2, \psi_{2,ik}}(\cdot)$ is also obtained from the *Gaussian-Chebyshev quadrature* approximation $\int_{-1}^1 \sqrt{1-x^2} g(x) dx \approx \sum_{i=1}^t w_i g(u_i)$. But note that $\Lambda_{\lambda_2, \psi_{2,ik}}(\cdot)$ is only determined by the density of SBSs, i. e. λ_2 .

C. Distance Distribution in Clustered UDN

For the cache-enabled mmWave UDN with clusters shown as Fig. 1 (b), the density of SBS is much higher than that of SCN. The clusters in UDN are formed by UTs and SBSs, where two independent PPPs, Φ_1 and Φ_2' , are included. In cluster \mathcal{A} , a UT has access to the contents stored at the caches of neighboring UTs and SBSs. Specifically, we consider the typical UT o , which is inserted at the center of cluster \mathcal{A} . This is shown in Fig. 3, where \mathcal{A} is a disc with radius d . Due to the TDM mechanism, only one link is allowed to be active within a cluster at one time. To differentiate UDN from the SCN scenario, we denote the density of SBSs PPP Φ_2' as λ_2' , where $\lambda_2' \gg \lambda_2$ [32]. Besides, without loss of generality, we assume that there exists at least one SBS within cluster \mathcal{A} . In what follows, we will first investigate the distribution of transmission distance for the typical UT. Then the distribution of SINR for UT o with mmWave channel will be given.

Considering UT o requesting content f in cluster \mathcal{A} , we denote the distance for the D2D tier between typical UT o and nearest UT which has content f as X_3 . The distance that o retrieves f from nearest SBS which stores f is denoted as X_4 . When f is not available in \mathcal{A} , the typical UT is served by the nearest SBS with distance X_5 . Then denoting $\bar{\lambda}'_{2,f} = \text{Pr}_{2,f} \lambda_2'$, we have the following results.

Lemma 4. *In clustered cache-enabled UDN, for typical UT requesting content f , which is located in the center of \mathcal{A} with radius d , the PDF $f_{X_3}(x)$ is the same with $f_{X_1}(x)$ given in (3), while the PDFs $f_{X_4}(x)$ and $f_{X_5}(x)$ are obtained by substituting $\bar{\lambda}_{1,f}$ with $\bar{\lambda}'_{2,f}$ and λ_2' in $f_{X_1}(x)$ respectively.*

Proof. Recalling the proof of Lemma 1, the only difference in UDN is that the density of SBSs becomes λ_2' . Based on the assumption $N_2 > 0$, the distributions $f_{X_4}(x)$ and $f_{X_5}(x)$ can be derived through calculating $\text{Pr}\{X_3 \leq x | \bar{N}_{2,f} \geq 1\}$ and $\text{Pr}\{X_4 \leq x | N_2 \geq 1\}$ respectively as given in (33), where $\bar{N}_{2,f}$ denotes the number of SBSs in \mathcal{A} which have content f . \square

D. SINR Distribution in mmWave UDN

Based on the distance distribution of content sharing given in Lemma 4, we then investigate the SINR distribution for the typical UT in cache-enabled mmWave UDN. Since only one link is active in each cluster at a time, there is at most one active SBS in neighboring clusters. Hence to ensure that the expected amount of SBSs in $\mathcal{D} = \Phi_2' \setminus \mathcal{A}$ is equal to the

Fig. 3: Content sharing within a cluster in cache-enabled mmWave UDN.

case where one SBS exists at each cluster in average sense, we let the density of SBS in \mathcal{D} be $\lambda_2^c = \frac{1}{\pi d^2}$. Besides, not all the SBSs in \mathcal{D} are active for serving due to the presence of D2D tier content exchanging. In order to characterize the SBSs which interfere UT o , we further thin the density of SBSs in area \mathcal{D} to $\bar{\lambda}'_{2,f} = \Xi \cdot \lambda_2^c$, where

$$\Xi = \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} p_f (1 - \text{Pr}_{1,f}) e^{-\bar{\lambda}_{1,f} \pi d^2}. \quad (14)$$

The Ξ represents the probability that a SBS is active. Let point $s \in \Phi_2 \setminus \mathcal{A}$ denote the interference SBS outside of disc \mathcal{A} . Thus the SINR experienced by the typical UT for three scenarios shown in Fig. 3 can be defined as

$$\Gamma_3 = \frac{P_1 G_0 x^{-\alpha_L} |h_0|^2}{I + \sigma^2}; \quad \Gamma_{4,5} = \frac{P_2 G_0 x^{-\alpha_L} |h_0|^2}{I + \sigma^2}, \quad (15)$$

where $I = \sum_{s \in \mathcal{D}} P_0 G r_s^{-\alpha_N} |h_u|^2$ is the inter-cluster interference with mmWave channel. P_0 is the average transmission power for SBSs within \mathcal{D} . The CDFs of Γ_j ($j = 3, 4, 5$) are given in Lemma 5¹.

Lemma 5. *In cache-enabled mmWave UDN, the CDF of $\Gamma_{3,4,5}$ for typical UT requesting f at cluster \mathcal{A} can be approximated as*

$$F_{\Gamma_j}(\gamma) \approx \sum_{m=0}^M \binom{M}{m} (-1)^m \sum_{i=1}^t w_i \Psi_{a_j, \bar{\lambda}'_{2,f}, b_j}(u_i), \quad j = 3, 4, 5, \quad (16)$$

where w_i and u_i are given in (7), and

$$a_3 = \bar{\lambda}'_{1,f}, b_3 = \psi_{1,1k}; \quad a_4 = \bar{\lambda}'_{2,f}, b_4 = \psi_{2,1k}; \quad a_5 = \lambda'_2, b_5 = \psi_{2,1k}. \quad (17)$$

Proof. Following the proof of Lemma 2, we can similarly obtain the results in (16) but with different density of interference SBSs and the densities given by (5). \square

The calculation of the interference in Lemma 5 by using the thinned density $\bar{\lambda}'_{2,f}$ is only an approximation to the true case. Comparing to F_{Γ_1} in (6), the CDFs $F_{\Gamma_{3,4,5}}$ have similar form. This is because the densities of SBSs with f and interference SBSs in \mathcal{D} in UDN are different from those in SCN.

It should be noted that when we account the interference in clustered cache-enabled SCN, we do not thin the density of SBSs λ_2 . This is due to the fact that the SBSs in SCN have much larger coverage than those in UDN, which makes $\Xi \rightarrow 1$. Besides, the CDFs given in Lemmas 2, 3 and 5 are only approximations. But with enlarging $t \rightarrow \infty$, the CDFs will coincide with the true value.

IV. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS AND OPTIMIZATION

In this section, we will derive the ergodic rate of a typical UT at a cluster for both cache-enabled mmWave SCN and UDN. Then the average service delay for typical UT will be studied.

¹For the case where there exists one SBS in typical cluster in SCN, the CDF of SINR can be similarly derived as F_{Γ_3} and F_{Γ_4} given in Lemma 5 but with settings of SCN. When typical UT is served by the SBS, the distribution for transmission distance should be obtained similar as X_4 in Lemma 4 but on the condition $N_2 = 1$.

A. Ergodic Rate Analysis

The ergodic rate refers to the mean data rate when adaptive modulation/coding is used over many fading realization for a given average SINR [57], which is given by

$$R = \mathbb{E}_\gamma [\log_2(1 + \min\{\gamma, \gamma_{\max}\})], \quad (18)$$

where $\gamma_{\max} = 2^{R_{\max}} - 1$ is the SINR threshold determined by practical constraints for the radio frequency circuit, and R_{\max} is the maximum achievable rate.

Theorem 1. *The ergodic rate of a typical UT in cluster \mathcal{A} for cache-enabled mmWave SCN and UDN is given by*

$$R_i = \frac{W}{\ln 2} \int_0^{\gamma_{\max}} \frac{1}{1 + \gamma} (1 - F_{\Gamma_i}(\gamma)) d\gamma, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \quad (19)$$

where $W_{1,3} = \frac{W}{N_d}$ and $W_{2,4,5} = W$.

Proof. From the proof of Proposition 3 in [27], we have

$$\begin{aligned} R_i &= \int_0^{\gamma_{\max}} W \log_2(1 + \gamma) f_{\Gamma_i}(\gamma) d\gamma \\ &= \frac{W}{\ln 2} \int_0^{\gamma_{\max}} \ln(1 + \gamma) f_{\Gamma_i}(\gamma) d\gamma \\ &= \frac{W}{\ln 2} \int_0^{\gamma_{\max}} \frac{1}{1 + \gamma} (1 - F_{\Gamma_i}(\gamma)) d\gamma, \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

which completes the proof. \square

Since the CDFs given in Lemmas 2, 3 and 5 are related to content f , (19) is the ergodic rate for the typical UT requesting f . Though Theorem 1 gives the expression of ergodic rate, the closed-form expression is hard to be obtained with the CDFs of $F_{\Gamma_{1,2,3}}(\gamma)$. Hence we consider the high SINR scenario for mmWave D2D and SBS tiers, and present the approximated result on ergodic rates.

Corollary 1. *In high SINR region, the ergodic rate of D2D tier for typical UT at cluster \mathcal{A} in cache-enabled mmWave SCN is approximated by*

$$R_1^+ = \frac{W_1}{\ln 2} \left(\left(1 + \Upsilon_{\bar{\lambda}_{1,f}, \lambda_2, \psi_{1,1k}}\right) \ln(1 + \gamma_{\max}) - \Upsilon_{\bar{\lambda}_{1,f}, \lambda_2, \psi_{1,1k}} \gamma_{\max} \right), \quad (21)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Upsilon_{\bar{\lambda}_{1,f}, \lambda_2, \psi_{1,1k}} &= \frac{\left(\bar{\lambda}_{1,f} \pi\right)^{-\frac{\alpha_L}{2}}}{1 - e^{-\bar{\lambda}_{1,f} \pi d^2}} \left(\frac{2\pi \lambda_2 d^{2-\alpha_N} \sum_{k,l \in \mathcal{M}} M^2 \text{Pr}_{lk} \psi_{1,1k}}{\alpha_N - 2} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{M \kappa \sigma^2}{P_1 G_0} \right) \left(\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{\alpha_L}{2}\right) - \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{\alpha_L}{2}, \bar{\lambda}_{1,f} \pi d^2\right) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Proof. See Appendix C the Proof of Corollary 1. \square

Under high SINR approximation, the closed-form expression of $\Upsilon_{\bar{\lambda}_{1,f}, \lambda_2, \psi_{1,1k}}$ can be obtained directly through integration without using *Gaussian-Chebyshev quadrature approximation* and *Gaussian Hypergeometric function*.

Corollary 2. In high SINR region, the ergodic rate of SBS tier for typical UT at cluster \mathcal{A} in cache-enabled mmWave SCN is approximated by

$$R_2^+ = \frac{W_2}{\ln 2} \left((1 + \Omega_{\lambda_2, \psi_{2,1k}}) \ln(1 + \gamma_{\max}) - \Omega_{\lambda_2, \psi_{2,1k}} \gamma_{\max} \right), \quad (23)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{\lambda_2, \psi_{2,1k}} &= \frac{2}{\alpha_N - 2} \left(\lambda_2 \pi d^2 + 1 \right) \sum_{k, l \in \mathcal{M}} M^2 \Pr_{lk} \psi_{2,1k} \\ &+ \frac{M \kappa \sigma^2 e^{\lambda_2 \pi d^2}}{P_2 G_0(\lambda_2 \pi)^{\frac{\alpha_N}{2}}} \Gamma \left(1 + \frac{\alpha_N}{2}, \lambda_2 \pi d^2 \right). \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Proof. This can be similarly proved by following the process of Appendix C but with substituting X_1, I_1 with X_2, I_2 and the corresponding distributions. \square

In clustered cache-enabled UDN, the ergodic rate of typical UT in high SINR region can be also derived with Lemma 5.

Corollary 3. In high SINR region, the ergodic rates R_j^+ ($j = 3, 4, 5$) of typical UT at cluster \mathcal{A} in cache-enabled mmWave UDN are derived as

$$R_j^+ = \frac{W_j}{\ln 2} \left(\left(1 + \Upsilon_{a_j, \tilde{\lambda}'_{2,f}, b_j} \right) \ln(1 + \gamma_{\max}) - \Upsilon_{a_j, \tilde{\lambda}'_{2,f}, b_j} \gamma_{\max} \right), \quad j = 3, 4, 5, \quad (25)$$

where (a_j, b_j) are given by (16).

Proof. Following the proof of Corollary 2, we can derive the final results by changing the densities of SBSs $(\tilde{\lambda}'_{2,f}, \lambda'_2)$ within \mathcal{A} and interference SBSs $(\tilde{\lambda}'_{2,f}, \lambda'_2)$ in \mathcal{D} . \square

It is worth noting that except for R_2 , the other ergodic rates given in Theorem 1 and Corollaries 1, 2 and 3 are derived with respect to (w.r.t.) the requested content f . Besides, the feasible domain for transmission power P_1 and P_2 can be obtained by letting $R_i^+ \geq 0$ ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$).

B. Service Delay Analysis

With the derived ergodic rates, the delay for two-nodes transmission is described as $T = l/R$. We then evaluate the average service delay for the typical UT² which is inserted at the center o of cluster \mathcal{A} .

Proposition 1. In cache-enabled mmWave SCN, the average service delay \bar{T}_1 for typical UT o at cluster \mathcal{A} is evaluated by

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{T}_1 &= \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} p_{n,f} (1 - \Pr_{1,f}) \left(\left(1 - e^{-\Pr_{1,f} \lambda_1 \pi d^2} \right) \frac{l}{R_1} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + e^{-\Pr_{1,f} \lambda_1 \pi d^2} \left(\frac{l}{R_2} + (1 - \Pr_{2,f}) T_0 \right) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

²The average service delay for UTs within cluster \mathcal{A} can also be analyzed in the similar way to the typical UT. Due to space limitation, we omit the details here.

In cache-enabled mmWave UDN, the average service delay \bar{T}_2 for typical UT at cluster \mathcal{A} is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{T}_2 &= \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} p_{n,f} (1 - \Pr_{1,f}) \left(\left(1 - e^{-\Pr_{1,f} \lambda_1 \pi d^2} \right) \frac{l}{R_3} + e^{-\Pr_{1,f} \lambda_1 \pi d^2} \right. \\ &\quad \left. \times \left(\left(1 - e^{-\Pr_{2,f} \lambda'_2 \pi d^2} \right) \frac{l}{R_4} + e^{-\Pr_{2,f} \lambda'_2 \pi d^2} \left(\frac{l}{R_5} + T_0 \right) \right) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Proof. In cache-enabled mmWave SCN, considering the request for content f from typical UT at center of cluster \mathcal{A} , the delay T_1 for fetching content from local cache, the UTs within \mathcal{A} , the cache of nearest SBS and the CN is 0, l/R_1 , l/R_2 and $l/R_2 + T_0$, respectively. Accordingly, the probability for delay T_1 is given by

$$\begin{cases} \Pr\{T_1 = 0\} = \Pr_{1,f}; \\ \Pr\{T_1 = l/R_1\} = (1 - \Pr_{1,f}) \Pr\{\bar{N}_{1,f} > 0\}; \\ \Pr\{T_1 = l/R_2\} = (1 - \Pr_{1,f}) \Pr\{\bar{N}_{1,f} = 0\} \Pr_{2,f}; \\ \Pr\{T_1 = l/R_2 + T_0\} = (1 - \Pr_{1,f}) \Pr\{\bar{N}_{1,f} = 0\} (1 - \Pr_{2,f}), \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

where T_0 is the consumed time for fetching content from CN. From the proof of Lemma 1, it has $\Pr\{\bar{N}_{1,f} = 0\} = e^{-\tilde{\lambda}'_{1,f} \pi d^2}$. Hence with the probability p_f for requesting content f , the average service delay \bar{T}_1 for typical UT in SCN is deduced in (26). Similarly, we can derive the expression for \bar{T}_2 . \square

Since all the rates R_i ($i = 1, 3, 4, 5$) except R_2 are determined by Θ_1 and Θ_2 , it is necessary to investigate how the performance of average service delay behaves with adjusting caching capacity.

Proposition 2. For fixed caching policy $\Pi_1(\Pi_2)$, the probability $\Pr_{1,f}(\Pr_{2,f})$ is non-decreasing with $\Theta_1(\Theta_2)$, while $\bar{T}_{1,2}$ are non-increasing with Θ_2 when $\frac{l}{R_3} \leq \frac{l}{R_4} \leq \frac{l}{R_5} + T_0$.

Proof. When $\Theta_1(\Theta_2)$ increases, more contents can be stored at UTs(SBSs). Hence $\Pr_{1,f}(\Pr_{2,f})$ will grow when $\Pi_1(\Pi_2)$ is fixed. This can also be shown by looking at the derivative of $\Pr_{1,f}$ for the policies described in Section V. Considering the average service delay \bar{T}_1 , the derivative satisfies $\frac{\partial \bar{T}_1}{\partial \Pr_{2,f}} < 0$. Since $\Pr_{2,f}$ is non-decreasing with Θ_2 from Proposition 1, it can be concluded that \bar{T}_1 is non-increasing with Θ_2 . As for the UDN scenario, it can be shown that when $\frac{l}{R_4} \leq \frac{l}{R_5} + T_0$, the average service delay \bar{T}_2 decreases with $\Pr_{2,f}$ (i. e. $\frac{\partial \bar{T}_2}{\partial \Pr_{2,f}} \leq 0$), while $\frac{\partial \bar{T}_2}{\partial \Pr_{1,f}} \leq 0$ under the condition $\frac{l}{R_3} \leq \frac{l}{R_4} \leq \frac{l}{R_5} + T_0$. \square

The condition presented in Proposition 2 demonstrates that for a typical UT in cache-enabled UDN, the delay of fetching content from the cache of SBS is smaller than D2D content share, while that of fetching content from CN is the largest. This condition can be easily satisfied when the density of SBSs is comparable with UTs in UDN. From the expressions of \bar{T}_1 and \bar{T}_2 , it is easy to find out that the advantage of enabling caching at SBSs is to offload backhauling to CN. Meanwhile the caching capability of UTs can determine the rates of UT both in clustered mmWave SCN and UDN. In what follows,

Algorithm 1: AO algorithm for (P1)

- 1: **Initialize:** $\{\text{Pr}_{2,f} = \frac{\Theta_2}{F} | f \in \mathcal{F}\}$;
 - 2: **for** Iteration $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ **do**
 - 3: **Step 1:** solve (P1) over \mathbf{Pr}_1 with fixed \mathbf{Pr}_2 ;
 - 4: **Step 2:** solve (P1) over \mathbf{Pr}_2 with fixed \mathbf{Pr}_1 ;
 - 5: **end for**
-

we study the caching policy which can minimize the service delay for typical UT.

Proposition 3. *We can obtain the optimal caching scheme that minimizes average service delays $\bar{T}_{1,2}$ by solving*

$$(P1) : \min_{\mathbf{Pr}_1, \mathbf{Pr}_2} \bar{T}_{1,2}, \quad (29a)$$

$$s.t. \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \text{Pr}_{1,f} = \Theta_1, \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \text{Pr}_{2,f} = \Theta_2; \quad (29b)$$

$$0 \leq \text{Pr}_{1,f} \leq 1, 0 \leq \text{Pr}_{2,f} \leq 1, f \in \mathcal{F}. \quad (29c)$$

Proof. The constraint (29c) is due to that $\text{Pr}_{1,f}$ and $\text{Pr}_{2,f}$ are probabilities. Suppose the constraints (29b) are not active, i. e. $\sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \text{Pr}_{1,f}^* < \Theta_1$, $\sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \text{Pr}_{2,f}^* < \Theta_2$ where $\mathbf{Pr}_{1,2}^*$ are optimal solution for (P1). Then we can always find i with $0 < \text{Pr}_{1,i}^* < 1$, and $\epsilon \in [0, \min(1 - \text{Pr}_{1,i}^*, \Theta_1 - \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \text{Pr}_{1,f}^*)]$. Since \bar{T}_1 increases over $\text{Pr}_{1,f}$ with fixed \mathbf{Pr}_2^* , we can substitute $\text{Pr}_{1,i}^*$ with $\text{Pr}_{1,i}^* + \epsilon$ to further reduce \bar{T}_1 . Similarly, with fixed \mathbf{Pr}_1^* , we can also introduce a small increment on some $\text{Pr}_{2,f}^*$ to reduce \bar{T}_1 . Hence the constraint (29b) must be active for the optimum. Following the same clue, it can be proved that the constraint (29b) should also be active in minimizing \bar{T}_2 . \square

Since \mathbf{Pr}_1 and \mathbf{Pr}_2 are coupled variables in objective (29a), the caching strategies of UTs and SBSs should be optimized jointly. We adopt an *Alternate Optimization* (AO) approach to solve (P1), which is concluded in Alg. 1. At the first step of each iteration, we optimize the caching policy of UTs with fixed caching scheme of SBSs. Then the caching policy of SBSs is optimized with updated \mathbf{Pr}_1 at the second step. It can be verified that the average service delay reduces at each iteration of Alg. 1. In high SINR region, where P_1 and P_2 are assumed to be large enough to make $R_i(f) \rightarrow R_{\max}$ ($i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}, \forall f \in \mathcal{F}$), we can obtain the approximation $\bar{T}_{1,2}$ by applying $R_i \rightarrow R_{\max}$ in (26) and (27).

Remark 1. *By substituting $\bar{T}_{1,2}$ with $\tilde{T}_{1,2}$ in (29a), the iterates $(\mathbf{Pr}_1^k, \mathbf{Pr}_2^k)$ generated in Algorithm 1 converges monotonically.*

Proof. Since the objectives $\tilde{T}_{1,2}$ are convex over \mathbf{Pr}_1 when \mathbf{Pr}_2 is fixed, and linearly decrease over \mathbf{Pr}_2 with fixed \mathbf{Pr}_1 , in each sub-step of one iteration in Algorithm 1, the objectives $\tilde{T}_{1,2}$ are monotonically non-increasing due to the minimization. Since the service delays $\tilde{T}_{1,2}$ are bounded below, the sequence $\{\tilde{T}_{1,2}(\mathbf{Pr}_1^k, \mathbf{Pr}_2^k)\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ converges to a limit value [58]. \square

It should be noted that Alg. 1 is a Probabilistic Caching (PC) based policy. Different from the PC scheme provided in [59], we jointly optimize the caching policy for SBSs and UTs to minimize the service delay for typical UT. With the output

$\mathbf{Pr}_1(\mathbf{Pr}_2)$ from Alg. 1, UTs(SBSs) randomly build a list of up to $\Theta_1(\Theta_2)$ contents to be cached as [59].

V. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In what follows, we will provide some numerical results to validate the analysis of distance and SINR distributions, and the ergodic rate for typical UT. Moreover, the effects of caching capacity and policies of SBSs and UTs, as well as the radius of clusters, on the average service delay for both cache-enabled mmWave SCN and UDN with clusters will be provided. The parameters used for simulations are given in Table I.

We consider homogeneous content preference among UTs with $\omega = \mathcal{F}$. Besides, we apply the proposed caching scheme Alg. 1, and the following caching policies for SBSs and UTs:

- *RC:* UTs(SBSs) choose to store contents randomly until $\Theta_1(\Theta_2)$ is occupied, where

$$\text{Pr}_{i,f} = \frac{\Theta_i}{F}, f \in \mathcal{F}. \quad (30)$$

- *Most popular caching (MPC):* UTs(SBSs) choose to store contents according to the order of ω until $\Theta_1(\Theta_2)$ is occupied, where

$$\text{Pr}_{i,f} = \begin{cases} 1, & f \in \bar{\omega}_{\Pi_i} = \{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_{\Theta_i}\}; \\ 0, & f \in \mathcal{F} \setminus \bar{\omega}_{\Pi_i}. \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

- *PC:* UTs(SBSs) store contents up to $\Theta_1(\Theta_2)$ according to the probabilistic content caching method as [59], but with the following probability

$$\text{Pr}_{i,f} = \min(p_f \Theta_i + \mu^*, 1), f \in \mathcal{F}, \quad (32)$$

where $\mu^*(\geq 0)$ is found to make $\sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \text{Pr}_{i,f} = \Theta_i$ satisfied.

Since we assume homogeneous content preference and caching capacity for UTs, the contents that are stored at UTs will be unique if the MPC scheme is adopted. Besides, to exploit the diversity of caching content at UTs, we adopt PC scheme for UTs, i. e., $\Pi_1 = \text{PC}$.

A. Distributions of distance and SINR

Fig. 4 presents the CDFs $F_{X_i}(x)$ with radius $d = 20$ m, $\eta = 1.2$, $\Theta_2 = 2$ Gb and $\Pi_2 = \text{PC}$. Since the distribution for X_1 and X_3 is the same, we show the CDFs of $X_{1,4,5}$ Fig. 4 (a). Because the transmission distance is within interval $(0, d]$, both CDFs have $F_{X_{1,4,5}}(d) = 1$. As for content $f = 10$, the probability $\text{Pr}_{1,f=10}$ is less than 1. The UTs which has content $f = 10$ follows the PPP $\bar{\Phi}_{1,f=10}$ with density $\text{Pr}_{1,f=10} \lambda_1 < \lambda_1$. Hence the CDF $F_{X_{1,f=10}}(x)$ is not larger than $F_{X_{1,f=1}}(x)$ with fixed x . With enlarging caching capacity Θ_1 , the probability $\text{Pr}_{1,f=10}$ is non-decreasing according to Proposition 1. This densifies the PPP $\bar{\Phi}_{1,f=10}$, which hence increases the CDFs $F_{X_1}(x)$. The CDF $F_{X_5}(x)$ is only determined by the density of SBS λ_2' . For the CDF $F_{X_4}(x)$, it is always smaller than $F_{X_5}(x)$ for fixed x since $\lambda_{2,f}' \leq \lambda_2'$. The CDF $F_{X_2}(x)$ is shown in Fig. 4 (b), which is only

determined by the density λ_2 . As the result shown, it has almost probability 1 for the typical UT to connect a SBS within distance 200 m in SCN.

Fig. 5 presents the CDFs $F_{F_i}(\gamma)$ for SINRs of typical UT in clustered SCN and UDN. We set $P_1 = 0$ dBm, $P_2 = 20$ dBm, $\eta = 1.2$, $f = 1$, $\Theta_1 = 0.5$ Gb, $\Theta_2 = 2$ Gb and $d = 10$ m. The CDFs $F_{F_i}(\gamma)$ in theory are obtained by applying integration on (35), (12) and variants of (35) directly. While $F_{F_i}(\gamma)$ in approximation are given in Lemmas 2, 3 and 5. From Fig. 5, it can be concluded that *Gaussian-Chebyshev quadrature* with $t = 30$ can provide accurate approximation for $F_{F_i}(\gamma)$. For $\alpha_L \in \{2.5, 3\}$ and $\Pi_2 = \{RC, PC\}$, the SINR of D2D tier for typical UT in mmWave SCN is expected to be larger than that of SBS tier and the SINR of typical UT in mmWave UDN. This is due to the truth that the interference experienced by the typical UT in mmWave UDN is stronger than that in SCN. When the pathloss exponent of LOS α_L increases to 3, the performance of SINR for all scenarios become worse. While the CDF $F_{F_2}(\gamma)$ keeps the same since it is only determined by the pathloss exponent of NLOS α_N . For the considered caching setup, the SINRs $F_{F_{1,3,4}}(\gamma)$ in both SCN and UDN scenarios with caching policy $\Pi_2 = PC$ are larger than those achieved by $\Pi_2 = RC$ policy. This is because with $\Pr_{2,f=1,\Pi_2=PC} \geq \Pr_{2,f=1,\Pi_2=RC}$, more SBSs will store content $f = 1$ when policy PC is adopted rather than RC. Hence the typical UT is likely to retrieve content $f = 1$ from a closer SBS with PC than RC, i. e. $\mathbb{E}_{X_{2,f=1,\Pi_2=PC}}[x] \leq \mathbb{E}_{X_{2,f=1,\Pi_2=RC}}[x]$ and $\mathbb{E}_{X_{4,f=1,\Pi_2=PC}}[x] \leq \mathbb{E}_{X_{4,f=1,\Pi_2=RC}}[x]$.

B. Ergodic Rates

We evaluate ergodic rates R_i and approximations R_i^+ with $\Pi_2 = PC$, $d = 20$ m, $\eta = 1.2$, $\alpha_L = 3$ and $\alpha_N = 3.5$. From the results presented in Fig. 5, we show that adopting PC policy at SBSs can achieve better SINR performance than RC for popular contents (e. g. $f = 1$). Hence we only consider the

Fig. 4: (a). CDFs of transmission distance $F_{X_{1,4,5}}(x)$; (b). CDF of transmission distance $F_{X_2}(x)$.

Fig. 5: CDFs of SINR $F_{F_{1,2,3,4,5}}(\gamma)$ for typical UT for both SCN and UDN scenarios.

Fig. 6: (a) Ergodic rate $R_{1,3}$ and approximation $R_{1,3}^+$; (b) ergodic rate $R_{2,4,5}$ and approximation $R_{2,4,5}^+$.

$\Pi_2 = PC$ policy here. The ergodic rates $R_{1,3}$ and $R_{1,3}^+$ are shown in Fig. 6 (a). As P_1 increases from -40 dBm to -10 dBm, the ergodic rate $R_1(f=2)$ and $R_3(f=2)$ will grow to the maximum achievable rate $R_{\max} = 2$ Gbps. Moreover, when P_1 is higher than -30 dBm, the approximation $R_1^+(f=2)$ approaches theory $R_1(f=2)$. As for $R_3^+(f=2)$, the gap from theory $R_3(f=2)$ becomes negligible when $P_1 > -15$ dBm. While Fig. 6 (b) shows the ergodic rate $R_{2,4,5}$ and approximation $R_{2,4,5}^+$. We can see that the approximation R_2^+ gets close to theoretical rate R_2 when $P_2 > 30$ dBm, where both R_2 and R_2^+ almost are R_{\max} . As for $R_{4,5}(f=10)$, the approximation approaches the theoretical rate when P_2 is larger than 10 dBm and -10 dBm, respectively.

Fig. 7: Average service delay for typical UT in clustered mmWave SCN and UDN w.r.t transmission power P_1 for D2D tier.

Fig. 9: Average service delay for typical UT in clustered mmWave SCN and UDN w.r.t the radius d of clusters.

Fig. 8: Average service delay for typical UT in clustered mmWave SCN and UDN w.r.t caching capacity Θ_2 .

C. Average Service Delay

In Fig. 7 we evaluate the average service delay for typical UT in clustered mmWave SCN and UDN w.r.t. the D2D tier transmission power P_1 . In the simulation, we set $P_2 = 10$ dBm, $\eta = 1.2$, $\Theta_1 = 0.5$ Gb, $\Theta_2 = 2$ Gb and $\alpha_L = 2.5$. For fixed radius $d = 10$ m, the average service delay for different caching policies satisfy $\bar{T}_{1,\text{MPC}} < \bar{T}_{1,\text{PC}} < \bar{T}_{1,\text{RC}}$ and $\bar{T}_{2,\text{MPC}} < \bar{T}_{2,\text{PC}} < \bar{T}_{2,\text{RC}}$. When the caching policies RC and PC are adopted by SBSs, the average service delay of typical UT in mmWave UDN is smaller than that in mmWave SCN, i. e., $\bar{T}_2 < \bar{T}_1$, when P_1 is larger than -15 dBm with $d = 10$ m. But with $\Pi_2 = \text{MPC}$ at SBSs and $P_1 \in [-40, -10]$ dBm, the average delay of typical UT in clustered UDN is smaller than that in SCN with $d = 10$ m. It is because that with $\Pi_2 = \text{MPC}$, more requests from the typical UT are served by the D2D tier both in clustered SCN and UDN than cases $\Pi_2 \in \{\text{RC}, \text{PC}\}$.

Furthermore, the interference for the typical UT in mmWave UDN is stronger than that in SCN. Hence the average delay presents the trend $\bar{T}_{2,\text{MPC}} < \bar{T}_{2,\text{MPC}}$ when P_1 is small enough, which can also explain the case $d = 15$ m.

By fixing $\Pi_2 = \text{PC}$, $P_1 = 0$ dBm and $P_2 = 20$ dBm, we present the average service delay over the caching capacity Θ_2 in Fig. 8. As shown in this figure, both delay \bar{T}_1 and \bar{T}_2 decrease with enlarging Θ_2 . This is because larger Θ_2 can offload more backhauling to CN. Besides, the delay can be reduced by enlarging Θ_1 . This phenomenon can be explained from two aspects. With a larger Θ_1 , more requests from typical UT can be served by its local cache, which consumes 0 s delay. Besides, the expected distance for D2D tier transmission will be shorten since the requested contents have higher probability to be cached by the neighboring UTs within the same cluster. When the shape parameter of Zipf-like distribution reduces from 1.2 to 0.9, the content preference of UTs becomes less concentrated. Hence the advantage brought by caching unit becomes weaken, which leads to a larger service delay.

Finally, we present the impact of radius d of clusters on the service delay for typical UT in SCN and UDN in Fig. 9, with $P_1 = 0$ dBm, $P_2 = 20$ dBm, $\alpha_L = 2.5$, $\Theta_1 = 0.5$ Gb and $\Theta_2 = 2$ Gb. When caching policies RC, PC and MPC are adopted at SBSs, the delays $\bar{T}_{1,2}$ decrease with d in range $[5, 15]$ m. The reason is that the increased amount of D2D tier content sharing can reduce the delay. Besides, the interference for typical UT is non-increasing with radius d for both mmWave SCN and UDN scenarios. However, service delay $\bar{T}_{2,\text{RC}}$, $\bar{T}_{2,\text{PC}}$ and $\bar{T}_{2,\text{MPC}}$ degrade by enlarging cluster size to $d > r_d = 15$ m. This is because multiple D2D links are allowed when $d > r_d$, and the D2D transmission bandwidth for the typical UT reduces due to spectrum partition. When the cluster size gets larger, we have $\bar{T}_{2,\text{RC}} < \bar{T}_{2,\text{PC}} < \bar{T}_{2,\text{MPC}}$ for UDN scenario. This demonstrates that with $\Pi_1 = \text{PC}$ and large caching capacity Θ_2 , the necessity for optimizing caching policy for SBSs decreased in UDN. In Fig. 9, the average service delay achieved by proposed caching policy Alg. 1 is smaller than that of caching scheme $\Pi_1 =$

PC, $\Pi_2 = \{\text{RC, PC, MPC}\}$ for both mmWave SCN and UDN scenarios. Besides, we simulate the service delay for MPPC scheme [60], which greedily store contents at SBSs and UTs to maximize the total hit-rate. As shown in Fig. 9, Alg. 1 outperforms MPPC for considered cluster size region. Note that the service delay achieved by Alg. 1 presents the similar trend with benchmarks $\Pi_1 = \text{PC}$, $\Pi_2 = \{\text{RC, PC, MPC}\}$, where the best performance can be achieved with radius $d = r_d$.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

We studied clustering schemes for cache-enabled mmWave SCN and UDN through investigating the ergodic rate and service delay for typical UT in a cluster. By defining the clusters as disjoint discs with equal size, the closed-form expressions of SINR distribution and ergodic rates in high SINR region are derived for both scenarios, which are characterized by the radius d of clusters, caching capacity of UTs and SBSs, and caching policies. Besides, we propose a PC based caching policy which jointly optimize the caching scheme for SBSs and UTs to minimize the service delay. Through analysis and simulations, we show that the average service delay of typical UT can be reduced by enlarging the caching capacity of UTs and SBSs. Moreover, we reveal that the service delay in cache-enabled mmWave UDN with clusters can lead a conditional performance gain compared with those in mmWave SCN due to deploying dense SBSs. It shows that the proposed caching scheme can further reduce the service delay of typical UT compared with benchmark policies. Moreover, simulation results show that there exists a best radius d on average service delay in mmWave SCN, which can guide the design of the clustering scheme.

APPENDIX A PROOF OF LEMMA 1

Denote $N_{1,2}(b(o, x))$ as the number of UT or SBS falling in $b(o, x)$, where $b(o, x)$ is the disc of radius x centered at o . For simplicity, we refer $N_{1,2}(b(o, d))$ as $N_{1,2}$. The D2D tier transmission happens only when the requested content exists in cluster \mathcal{A} . Considering $\text{Pr}_{1,f}$ which represents the probability that f exists at any UTs, we thin the Φ_1 by deleting each UT with probability $\text{Pr}_{1,f}$ to obtain a new PPP denoted as $\overline{\Phi}_{1,f}$, which has density $\overline{\lambda}_{1,f} = \text{Pr}_{1,f} \lambda_1$ and consists of the UTs with f . Denote $\overline{N}_{1,f}(b(o, x))$ as the number of UT in $\overline{\Phi}_{1,f}$ located within disc $b(o, x)$ while $\overline{N}_{1,f} = \overline{N}_{1,f}(b(o, d))$. The probability $\text{Pr}\{X_1 \leq x | \overline{N}_{1,f} \geq 1\}$ conditioned on $\overline{N}_{1,f} \geq 1$ implies that there exists at least one UT with content f in area \mathcal{A} with radius d , which is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Pr}\{X_1 \leq x | \overline{N}_{1,f} \geq 1\} &= 1 - \text{Pr}\{X_1 > x | \overline{N}_{1,f} \geq 1\} \\ &= 1 - \frac{\text{Pr}\{X_1 > x\} - \text{Pr}\{X_1 > x, \overline{N}_{1,f} = 0\}}{\text{Pr}\{\overline{N}_{1,f} \geq 1\}} \\ &= 1 - \frac{\text{Pr}\{\overline{N}_{1,f}(b(o, x)) = 0\} - \text{Pr}\{\overline{N}_{1,f} = 0\}}{1 - \text{Pr}\{\overline{N}_{1,f} = 0\}} \quad (33) \\ &= \frac{1 - e^{-\overline{\lambda}_{1,f} \pi x^2}}{1 - e^{-\overline{\lambda}_{1,f} \pi d^2}}. \end{aligned}$$

Then we can obtain the PDF of X_1 as shown in (3).

Next we derive the distribution of distance X_2 for SBS tier transmission. Denote N_2 as the number of SBS within cluster \mathcal{A} . The probability $\text{Pr}\{X_2 \leq x | N_2 = 0\}$ conditioned on $N_2 = 0$ implies that there is no SBS located in area \mathcal{A} with radius d , which is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Pr}\{X_2 \leq x | N_2 = 0\} &= 1 - \frac{\text{Pr}\{X_2 > x, N_2 = 0\}}{\text{Pr}\{N_2 = 0\}} \\ &= 1 - \frac{\text{Pr}\{N_2(b(o, x)) = 0\}}{\text{Pr}\{N_2 = 0\}} \quad (34) \\ &= 1 - e^{-\lambda_2 \pi (x^2 - d^2)}. \end{aligned}$$

According to the above expression, the PDF of X_2 can be derived as (4).

APPENDIX B PROOF OF LEMMA 2

The CDF of I_1 can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} F_{I_1}(\gamma) &= 1 - \text{Pr}\left\{\frac{P_1 G_0 x^{-\alpha_L} |h_0|^2}{I_1 + \sigma^2} > \gamma\right\} \\ &= 1 - \text{Pr}\left\{|h_0|^2 > \frac{(I_1 + \sigma^2)\gamma}{P_1 G_0 x^{-\alpha_L}}\right\} \\ &\stackrel{(a)}{\approx} 1 - \mathbb{E}_{X_1, I_1} \left[1 - \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\kappa \gamma (I_1 + \sigma^2)}{P_1 G_0 x^{-\alpha_L}}} \right)^M \right] \\ &\stackrel{(b)}{\approx} \sum_{m=0}^M \binom{M}{m} (-1)^m \mathbb{E}_{X_1} \left[\mathbb{E}_{I_1} \left[e^{-\frac{m \kappa \gamma I_1}{P_1 G_0 x^{-\alpha_L}}} \right] e^{-\frac{m \kappa \gamma \sigma^2}{P_1 G_0 x^{-\alpha_L}}} \right], \quad (35) \end{aligned}$$

where (a) follows from the CDF approximation of normalized gamma random variable $|h_0|^2 \sim \text{Gamma}(M, \frac{1}{M})$ [54], and (b) follows from the *Binomial Theorem*. The term B_1 in (35) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}_{I_1} \left[e^{-\frac{m \kappa \gamma I_1}{P_1 G_0 x^{-\alpha_L}}} \right] &= \mathbb{E}_{s \in \mathcal{D}_1} \left[\prod_{s \in \mathcal{D}_1} \mathbb{E}_{G, h_u} \left[e^{-\frac{m \kappa \gamma P_0 G r_s^{-\alpha_N} |h_u|^2}{P_1 G_0 x^{-\alpha_L}}} \right] \right] \\ &\stackrel{(c)}{=} \mathbb{E}_{s \in \mathcal{D}_1} \left[\prod_{s \in \mathcal{D}_1} \sum_{l, k \in \mathcal{M}} \text{Pr}_{lk} \mathbb{E}_{h_u} \left[e^{-\frac{m \kappa \gamma P_0 G l g_k r_s^{-\alpha_N} |h_u|^2}{P_1 G_0 x^{-\alpha_L}}} \right] \right] \\ &\stackrel{(d)}{=} \mathbb{E}_{s \in \mathcal{D}_1} \left[\prod_{s \in \mathcal{D}_1} \sum_{l, k \in \mathcal{M}} \text{Pr}_{lk} (1 + \gamma m \psi_{1, lk} x^{\alpha_L} r_s^{-\alpha_N})^{-M} \right] \\ &\stackrel{(e)}{=} e^{-\lambda_2 \sum_{l, k \in \mathcal{M}} \text{Pr}_{lk} \int_d^\infty \int_0^{2\pi} (1 - (1 + \gamma m \psi_{1, lk} x^{\alpha_L} r_s^{-\alpha_N})^{-M}) r_s dr_s d\theta} \\ &\stackrel{(f)}{=} e^{-\pi \lambda_2 \sum_{l, k \in \mathcal{M}} \text{Pr}_{lk} d^2 \left({}_2F_1 \left(M, -\frac{2}{\alpha_N}; 1 - \frac{2}{\alpha_N}; -\gamma m \psi_{1, lk} x^{\alpha_L} d^{-\alpha_N} \right) - 1 \right)}, \quad (36) \end{aligned}$$

where (c) follows from the expectation of the antenna gain G , (d) follows from the moment-generating function of gamma distribution, (e) follows from the probability generating functional of a PPP [61], and (f) is from the property of *Gaussian Hypergeometric function* and holds for $\alpha_L, \alpha_N > 2$.

Then plugging (36) into (6) and taking expectation over X_1 , we obtain the CDF as

$$\begin{aligned}
F_{\Gamma_1}(\gamma) &\approx \sum_{m=0}^M \binom{M}{m} (-1)^m \int_0^d f_{X_1}(x) e^{-\frac{m\kappa\gamma\sigma^2}{P_1 G_0 x^{-\alpha_L}}} \\
&\times e^{-\pi\lambda_2 \sum_{l,k \in \mathcal{M}} \text{Pr}_{lk} d^2 \left({}_2F_1 \left(M, -\frac{2}{\alpha_N}; 1 - \frac{2}{\alpha_N}; -\gamma m \psi_{1,lk} x^{\alpha_L} d^{-\alpha_N} \right) - 1 \right)} dx \\
&\stackrel{(g)}{\approx} \sum_{m=0}^M \binom{M}{m} (-1)^m \sum_{i=1}^t w_i \Psi_{\bar{\lambda}_{1,f}, \lambda_2, \psi_{1,lk}}^-(u_i), \tag{37}
\end{aligned}$$

where (g) is obtained by invoking approximation of *Gaussian-Chebyshev quadrature*, which follows $\int_{-1}^1 \sqrt{1-x^2} g(x) dx \approx \sum_{i=1}^t w_i g(u_i)$. w_i , u_i and $\Psi_{\bar{\lambda}_{1,f}, \lambda_2, \psi_{1,lk}}^-(u_i)$ are given in (7) and (8) respectively.

APPENDIX C PROOF OF COROLLARY 1

From (35) and (36), the CDF of Γ_1 in high SINR region can be derived as

$$\begin{aligned}
F_{\Gamma_1}(\gamma) &\approx \mathbb{E}_{X_1, I_1} \left[\left(1 - e^{-\frac{\kappa\gamma(I_1 + \sigma^2)}{P_1 G_0 x^{-\alpha_L}}} \right)^M \right] \\
&\stackrel{(a)}{\approx} \mathbb{E}_{X_1, I_1} \left[\frac{M\kappa\gamma(I_1 + \sigma^2)}{P_1 G_0 x^{-\alpha_L}} \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E}_{X_1} \left[\mathbb{E}_{s \in \mathcal{D}_1} \left[\sum_{s \in \mathcal{D}_1} \mathbb{E}_{G, h_u} \left[\frac{M\kappa\gamma P_0 G |h_u|^2}{P_1 G_0 x^{-\alpha_L} r_s^{\alpha_N}} \right] \right] + \frac{M\kappa\gamma\sigma^2}{P_1 G_0 x^{-\alpha_L}} \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E}_{X_1} \left[\mathbb{E}_{s \in \mathcal{D}_1} \left[\sum_{s \in \mathcal{D}_1} \sum_{k, l \in \mathcal{M}} \frac{M^2 \text{Pr}_{lk} \psi_{1,lk} \gamma}{x^{-\alpha_L} r_s^{\alpha_N}} \right] + \frac{M\kappa\gamma\sigma^2}{P_1 G_0 x^{-\alpha_L}} \right] \\
&\stackrel{(b)}{=} \mathbb{E}_{X_1} \left[\lambda_2 \int_d^\infty \int_0^{2\pi} \sum_{k, l \in \mathcal{M}} \frac{M^2 \text{Pr}_{lk} \psi_{1,lk} \gamma}{x^{-\alpha_L} r_s^{\alpha_N - 1}} dr_s d\theta + \frac{M\kappa\gamma\sigma^2}{P_1 G_0 x^{-\alpha_L}} \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E}_{X_1} \left[\left(\frac{2\pi\lambda_2 d^{2-\alpha_N} \sum_{k, l \in \mathcal{M}} M^2 \text{Pr}_{lk} \psi_{1,lk} \gamma}{\alpha_N - 2} + \frac{M\kappa\gamma\sigma^2}{P_1 G_0} \right) x^{\alpha_L} \right] \\
&= \frac{(\bar{\lambda}_{1,f} \pi)^{-\frac{\alpha_L}{2}}}{1 - e^{-\bar{\lambda}_{1,f} \pi d^2}} \left(\frac{2\pi\lambda_2 d^{2-\alpha_N} \sum_{k, l \in \mathcal{M}} M^2 \text{Pr}_{lk} \psi_{1,lk}}{\alpha_N - 2} + \frac{M\kappa\sigma^2}{P_1 G_0} \right) \\
&\times \left(\Gamma \left(1 + \frac{\alpha_L}{2} \right) - \Gamma \left(1 + \frac{\alpha_L}{2}, \bar{\lambda}_{1,f} \pi d^2 \right) \right) \gamma, \tag{38}
\end{aligned}$$

where (a) follows from the approximation of $(1 - \exp(-x))^M \approx Mx$ when $x \rightarrow 0$, $\Gamma(x)$ is the *gamma function*, and (b) is since the truth that $\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{x \in \Phi} f(x) \right] = \lambda \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f(x) dx$, where λ is the density of PPP Φ . Then substituting (38) into (19) the desired result for R_1^+ can be obtained. Similarly integrating Lemmas 3 and 5, the expressions for R_2^+ can be similarly derived but with different constant C_2 .

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